

How to Improve Primary School Students' Self-Regulated Ability in the English Learning

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Abstract: *At present, with the deepening of the new curriculum reform, whose aim is to cultivate students' self-regulated learning ability, we can clearly discern many differences in the new textbooks, which puts forward new requirements for students and teachers, requiring students to collect information and solve problems independently and requiring teachers to effectively guide students to solve problems themselves. This paper attempts to discuss the problems existing in primary school students' English learning, the affecting factors and the ways to improve primary school students' regulated learning ability of English, so as to explore the ways to improve primary school students' regulated learning ability of English.*

Keywords: *Self-regulated learning ability; Primary school students; Strategy*

1. Introduction

Self-regulated learning is a modern learning mode corresponding to traditional acceptance learning. As the name implies, self-regulated learning takes students as the main body of learning and achieves its learning objectives through students' independent analysis, exploration, questioning, and creation. The Outline of Basic Education Curriculum Reform points out when discussing the reform of basic education curriculum, we should change the current situation of curriculum implementation which emphasizes too much acceptance of learning, rote learning, and mechanical practice, and we should advocate students' active participation, willingness to explore and diligence in doing things, cultivating students' ability to collect and process information, to acquire new knowledge, analyze and solve problems, and so on. However, the traditional English education emphasizes the receptive and passive learning style. We must change the past tendency of "over-emphasizing acceptance learning", but we need to advocate that students learn to study independently, rather than completely deny acceptance learning^[1-3].

Nowadays, our country vigorously advocates "people-oriented" and "quality-oriented education", while quality-oriented education is student-centered education, students are the masters of learning, and students should explore and think independently in teaching activities, but the reality is quite different. This is because many teachers are under the pressure of exam-oriented education, and most primary schools neglect the cultivation of students' self-regulated learning ability^[5-6]. Teachers still adopt traditional indoctrinating teaching methods in teaching, so that students can develop the habit of mechanically accepting foreign knowledge, thinking and learning behavior, and they subconsciously rely on teachers. It results in weak awareness of active learning, lack of self-exploration ability, lack of students' initiative and innovation ability, which is contrary to the concept of quality education advocated by our country. Teachers, as guides in students' learning activities, should change traditional teaching concepts and fully reflect the students' principal position in teaching. Teachers only play a leading role in teaching, so that students can achieve the goal of learning knowledge and maximize the value of life in self-learning. We must have a sufficient understanding of the cultivation of students' self-regulated ability, and it is necessary to take the cultivation of students' self-regulated learning ability as our unremitting goal.

2. Factors Influencing Primary School Students' English Self-regulated Learning Ability

There are many factors influencing primary school students' English regulated learning ability, in the paper some key factors are discussed as follows.

2.1 Pupils' factors

2.1.1 Cognition level

In terms of the characteristics of pupils' physical and mental development, the primary school students' cognitive level is still immature. Primary school students' attention span is short, the storage time of knowledge at this stage is very limited, and the storage capacity is small, therefore it is possible to learn the content of one lesson and forget the next

one completely, which undoubtedly brings great difficulties to pupils' English learning. Besides, pupils are weak in the use of meta-cognitive learning strategy and most of them cannot control, plan, regulate and monitor their own English studies like teenagers or adult students.

2.1.2 Learning motivation

Learning motivation is an important factor affecting pupils' self-regulated learning of English, and it is also the driving force of self-regulated learning. The vast majority of primary school students' motivation belongs to direct motivation. According to the psychological characteristics of pupils at this stage, they do not know how to link their learning with the future of individuals and countries. Therefore, as parents and teachers, primary school students should be guided according to their own characteristics, seize this feature, make full use of their direct motivation to stimulate their learning, on the other hand, teachers should patiently teach them, and gradually let them have long-term motivation.

2.1.3 Self-awareness.

Self-awareness is also one of the factors affecting pupils' self-regulated learning ability. Self-awareness is a fairly stable and comprehensive understanding of oneself formed in the long life of an individual, which includes pupils' stability, comprehensive ability, self-confidence in learning, self-monitoring and so on. This self-evaluation has a great impact on pupils. If teachers can adopt a more encouraging and less critical attitude at this time, it will help students to establish a positive self-concept and confidence in self-learning, so that they can have a strong interest in self-learning and lay a good foundation for their future life-long learning. Nevertheless, in this period, pupils' self-control ability is still very poor, which needs the careful cultivation of teachers and parents.

2.1.4 Learning strategy

Learning strategy is one of the internal factors that affect pupils' regulated learning. The degree of pupils' own cognitive strategies and their level of acquisition are the reasons that affect pupils' self-regulated learning. At this stage, the level and degree of pupils' acceptance of knowledge and the internalization of knowledge directly affect the learning effect of pupils. Therefore, the more cognitive, meta-cognitive, and social affective strategies pupils possess and the better their acquisition level, the better their self-regulated learning ability will be.

2.2 Teachers' factors

Under the current teaching system, many teachers still adopt the traditional teaching mode. Their teaching style is a typical "jar and mug" teaching method. They think that with this teaching method they can quickly transmit knowledge to students. For students, it is a time-saving and labor-saving efficient learning method. In such a class, which is completely controlled by teachers, students only need to learn what the teacher says. In this kind of mechanical learning, it seems simple and efficient, but actually, it is not the case. Students just memorize these words mechanically in their minds, rather than knowing them thoroughly. And students' self-regulated learning ability is highly impeded.

2.3 Parents' Neglect

The family factor is an important aspect of influencing pupils' self-regulated ability cultivation and academic achievement as well. Nowadays in China's exam-oriented society, most parents are greatly concerned about their children's study by planning children's study schedule, dominating children's life and consequently neglecting children's self-regulated learning skills. And even some parents do not think English study is important and they have no specific requirements for their children and they seriously lack educational methods in educating their children. Because of the weakness of family education, the pupils' self-regulated ability cultivation is difficult to achieve.

3. Strategies to Improve Primary school Students' English Self-regulated Learning Ability

Based on the exploration of key factors influencing the primary school students' self-regulated ability in the English learning, some ways are put forward to improve pupils' self-regulated ability.

3.1 To Change Teachers' Traditional Educational Concepts

Modern society is a multi-cultural and complex society, which requires us to have independent thinking ability. Teachers, as disseminators of knowledge, should keep pace with the times and impart the latest and best knowledge to students. Therefore, teachers should change their traditional educational concepts and try to train students to become new educational talents with all-rounded development based on the theory in the new curriculum standard. The

traditional concept of teacher-centered education is no longer suitable for the needs of today's world development, which limits the development of students' personality, makes them confined in a closed environment, and frustrates students' enthusiasm for learning. We should establish the concept of student-centered teaching, and realize the transformation from the traditional teaching-centered concept of teachers to the student-centered concept of learning. In teaching, the central position of teachers should give way to students' self-regulated learning, encourage and promote the development of students' self-regulated learning ability, become a guide, helper, and assistant of students' regulated learning, instead of the inculcator of knowledge. Teachers' duty is not to "teach", but to teach students how to learn, such as how to master, how to quickly learn and learn good skills. Only when students master the ability of "learning", can they truly become masters of learning and beneficiaries of "self-regulated learning".

3.2 To Strengthen the Guidance of Self-regulated Learning Methods

Only by mastering learning methods, can self-learning become possible. Therefore, teachers must strengthen the guidance of learning methods. The guiding learning method is to teach students to learn, that is, learn to read, think, search, and regulate. Firstly, reading is the basis of learning. Teaching is essentially to teach students to learn self-regulated learning, and the basis of self-regulated learning is the cultivation of students' reading ability. Secondly, retrieval is a means of learning. In the information age, learning directional retrieval is a necessary learning method for modern people. Teachers should draw up some topics in a planned way, let students go to the library or the network to search for information, select information, extract useful information, obtain information, process information, and carry out independent learning. Thirdly, regulation is the guarantee of learning. A stable mood and a peaceful mind are beneficial to learning. In the process of self-study, students objectively evaluate themselves, not only understand their strengths but also see their shortcomings. They can formulate goals, take measures, constantly adjust their mentality and control their behavior, so that they gradually become excellent students with both character and learning. There are many ways of self-regulated learning, generally including but not limited to reading, listening, research, observation, goal practice, and other means. Teachers should guide and help pupils to master the basic methods of self-regulated learning, that is, learning to set goals, formulate learning plans, strengthen time management, integrate and utilize resources, check-up, self-evaluation, and ultimately achieve the goal of learning self-reliance.

3.3 To Arrange Pre-class Preview Tasks Reasonably

Teachers should arrange pre-class preview tasks for students in accordance with the teaching objectives reasonably so that students have a goal when they study in class. In such learning, they can easily understand where they are clear in studying and where they can't understand themselves, so when teachers are in this class, they will listen carefully, actively integrate into the classroom, develop good teacher-student interaction, and enthusiastically put forward their own misunderstandings in the classroom, so that democracy between teachers and students will be launched. In the process of discussion, teachers should pay attention to building a democratic environment. In a free atmosphere, the whole discussion process should be relaxed and pleasant. Teachers should not laugh at students' wrong judgments or ideas. At the same time, teachers should not be arbitrary but listen to the students patiently. When arranging a pre-class preview for students, teachers should fully consider the existing level of students, reasonably grasp the difficulty of preview content and reasonable time arrangement. In this way, students will not lose confidence because the preview task is too difficult. It will not be too simple and tedious, both of which are not conducive to the improvement of students' self-regulated learning ability. Reasonable preview tasks can not only enable students to preview the content of new lessons but also review the past and know the new, consolidate and summarize the knowledge they have learned, so as to improve the cultivation of self-learning ability and lay a good foundation for future lifelong learning.

3.4 To Encourage Students to Get Rid of Their Dependence on Teachers and parents

In the process of teaching, it is easy to find that many students have a strong dependence on teachers. They are seldom willing to use their brains, and when they encounter problems, they always wait for others to solve them. When teachers pose questions, they are reluctant to think about problems that are slightly more difficult. As long as they read them once, they will put them aside. They do other things, waiting for teachers or students to tell them the answer. We often can see these situations as well, for example, parents help children to do homework. These happen mainly

because students have no confidence in their own learning, and have a strong dependence on others. In the final analysis, this consequence is largely due to the teachers' teaching way and parents' upbringing. Under the current exam-oriented education system, teachers mainly adopt the traditional teaching method in the teaching process, always stuffing knowledge to students blindly, ignoring the physical and mental development of students, so that students have long been accustomed to passive acceptance. Therefore, teachers should believe in students and give them a space for self-exploration so that they are no longer a passive connection in life. Parents also should encourage their children to solve problems through their own efforts rather than help them remove obstacles.

3.5 To Guide Students to Solve Problems through Various Channels

With the rapid development of electronic products and the popularity of the Internet, as long as we want to know any aspect of consulting, as long as we pick up the smartphone or search the Internet, there will be a lot of information for our reference. With the Internet, we can find the information we want anytime and anywhere. It can be said that the development of the Internet has brought great convenience to our study. So we should make full use of this resource. When they cannot get it from paper materials, teachers can encourage students to find what they want through the Internet. Another great advantage of the Internet is that many resources are free, so this undoubtedly brings great benefits to students. Besides, teachers can encourage students to read more simple English books, which will be conducive to the development of their thinking in English. Pupils can refer to a dictionary to solve the problem when they encounter words they don't know or understand. If it permits, pupils can use learning machine, mobile phone APP and other electronic devices to learn and solve doubts. Teachers can arrange relevant learning tasks in a planned way so that students can independently solve difficult problems by using dictionaries and electronic devices to search for information, and let students use the Internet to retrieve and download documents. Long-term persistence will help develop a good habit of solving problems independently.

4. Conclusion

In a word, how to improve students' regulated learning ability is a problem worthy of further study in English teaching institutes. How to let students "learn" is a problem worthy of our joint efforts to solve. Students' regulated learning ability needs joint efforts from various aspects, not only the careful cultivation of teachers but also the efforts of students themselves. Teachers should give students more freedom to explore. Meanwhile, students should persevere and strive to form a good habit of thinking independently.

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